

INTERACTION OF AROMATIC HYDROXY KETONES AND THEIR
DERIVATIVES AND THIONYL CHLORIDE IN PRESENCE OF
FINELY DIVIDED COPPER. PART XII. PREPARATION
OF 2:2'-DIHYDROXY-3:3'-DIACETYL-4:4'-DIMETHOXY-
DIPHENYL THIOETHER AND DERIVATIVES

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2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dimethoxydiphenyl thioether and its diacetyl, dimethyl and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives have been prepared. Its constitution has been established by nitration and bromination.

During investigation in this line of work (*vide* this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 807) it was observed that the ketonic group in the γ -position in resorcinol greatly activated the molecule, as no definite product could be isolated even though the reaction with thionyl chloride in the presence of copper was carried out at a very low temperature in the case of 2-acetylresorcinol. When, however, the reaction was carried out with the monomethyl ether of 2-acetylresorcinol, the thioether (I) was obtained. Its constitution has been established by nitration, yielding 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-6-methoxyacetophenone (III), proved by mixed melting point with the genuine specimen of the compound prepared by the method of Naik, Thakore and Shah (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 37A, 765). The diacetyl, dimethyl and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives of (I) have also been prepared.

Action of bromine in acetic acid medium on the thioether (I) furnished the dibromo thioether (II) which with nitric acid afforded a bromo-nitro derivative, free from sulphur, and identical with the bromo derivative obtained from (III) by the action of bromine. It has been assigned the constitution 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-5-bromo-6-methoxyacetophenone, based on rules of substitution. (II) is therefore 5:5'-dibromo derivative of (I).

Bromine in acetic acid medium at a higher temperature afforded a tetrabromo derivative without sulphur in it, and which lost two bromine atoms on boiling with aqueous potassium hydroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2'-Dihydroxy-3:3'-diacetyl-4:4'-dimethoxydiphenyl Thioether (I).—Finely divided copper (6 g.) was gradually added to the solution of thionyl chloride (9 c. c.) in dry chloroform (60 c. c.), cooled in an ice-bath. After about half an hour, 2-hydroxy-6-methoxyacetophenone (10 g.) was added to it at room temperature and the mixture was left overnight. It was filtered and the residue washed with dry chloroform. After removal of chloroform (at room temperature) a yellow paste remained behind. It was first treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°) and the residue was then treated with acetic acid, when a yellow powder separated out. It was crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow shining needles, m. p. 184-85°, yield, 2.5 g. (Found: C, 59.92; H, 5.0; S, 9.08. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6S$ requires C, 59.68; H, 4.97; S, 8.84 %).

It is soluble in dilute NaOH solution. It shows a bottle green coloration with EtOH-FeCl₃.

The same thioether was also formed when the solution of the ketone (3 g.) in dry ether (50 c. c.), cooled in ice, was treated with sulphur monochloride or sulphur dichloride (1.5 g.) and the reaction was allowed to proceed at that temperature for 1 hour and then the mixture was left overnight at room temperature. The paste obtained after removal of the ether from the filtrate was worked up as above, yield 0.6 g.

Diacetyl derivative (I) was prepared by heating on a boiling water-bath for half an hour the solution of the thioether (0.5 g.) in acetic anhydride (5 c. c.) in presence of a drop of H₂SO₄ (conc.). It crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (40°-60°) in colorless plates, m. p. 106-107°. (Found: S, 7.24. C₂₂H₂₂O₈S requires S, 7.17 %).

It did not show any colour with alcoholic EtOH-FeCl₃, nor dissolved in NaOH solution.

Dimethyl ether of the thioether (I) was prepared by refluxing on the water-bath the solution of the thioether (I:0.5 g.) in dry acetone (25 c.c.) with dimethyl sulphate (0.5 c. c.) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.). The solid obtained from the filtrate was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m. p. 135-36°. (Found: S, 8.07. C₂₀H₂₂O₈S requires S, 8.2 %).

It did not develop any colour with EtOH-FeCl₃, nor dissolve in NaOH solution.

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of (I) was obtained as orange needles, m. p. 230-31°. (Found: N, 15.56; S, 4.2. C₃₀H₂₆O₁₂N₈S requires N, 15.52; S, 4.43 %).

2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-6-methoxyacetophenone (III).—The thioether (I: 1 g.) was gradually added to nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 10 c.c.), cooled in ice. The reaction was then allowed to proceed at that temperature for about 10 minutes and the mixture was poured over crushed ice. The yellow solid obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in cream-coloured needles, m. p. 102-103°. (Found: N, 6.5. Calc. for C₉H₇O₅N: N, 6.63 %). Mixed m. p. with the genuine specimen showed no lowering in m. p. (Naik, Thakore and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

The *thioether* (II) was formed when acetic acid solution of bromine (5 c. c. of 20 % w/v) was added to the hot solution of the thioether (I: 1 g.) in acetic acid (20 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. The solid obtained on dilution was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 199-200°. (Found: Br, 30.59; S, 6.25. C₁₈H₁₆O₈Br₂S requires Br, 30.77; S, 6.15 %).

2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-5-bromo-6-methoxyacetophenone.—The solution of the thioether (II: 0.5 g.) in acetic acid (5 c. c.) was cooled in ice and nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 5 c.c.) was added to it at that temperature. The reaction was allowed to proceed at that temperature for about 10 minutes and then the mixture was poured over crushed ice when a yellow solid was obtained. This was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 156-57°. (Found: N, 4.7; Br, 27.43. Calc. for C₉H₇O₅NBr: N, 4.83; Br, 27.58 %). Mixed m. p. with the monobromo derivative obtained by the action of acetic acid solution of bromine (4 c.c. of 20 % w/v) on the solution of 2-hydroxy-3-nitro-6-methoxyacetophenone (III: 1 g.) in acetic acid (5 c. c.) at room temperature showed no depression.

2-Hydroxy-6-methoxytetrabromoacetophenone was formed when the solution of bromine (2 c.c.) in acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added to the solution of the thioether (I : 1 g.) in acetic acid (20 c. c.), and the mixture heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 hours. The solid obtained on dilution of the reaction mixture was crystallised from dilute alcohol in lemon-yellow needles, m. p. 101-102°. (Found : Br, 66.18. $C_8H_6O_4Br_4$ requires Br, 66.39 %). A known weight of the tetra bromoderivative was boiled for 2 hours with a 20% KOH solution (excess) and then acidified with nitric acid, and bromine in aqueous solution was estimated. (Found : Br, 33.9. Calc for 2 Br in $C_8H_6O_4Br_4$: Br, 33.2 %).

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Received March 6, 1956